

Studies in influence of ionic strength of medium on the complex equilibria of substituted hydroxy-1,3-propanediones with Cr^{III} and La^{III} metal ions pH metrically

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Abstract : The solution studies (the proton-ligand stability constant pK and metal-ligand stability constants log K) of binary (1 : 1) complexes of Cr^{III} and La^{III} with 1-(2'-hydroxy-5'-bromophenyl)-3-(2'-chlorophenyl)-1,3-propanedione [HB2CP] [L₁] and 1-(2'-hydroxy-5'-bromophenyl), 3-(4'-nitrophenyl)-1,3-propanedione [HB4NP] [L₂] have been performed at 0.02 to 0.1 mol dm⁻³ ionic strength at (29 ± 0.1 °C) in 70% dioxane-water mixture pH-metrically. The pK and log K values are utilized to estimate the thermodynamic stability constants at zero ionic strength and to know the exact nature of complexation equilibria.

Keywords : Ionic strength, substituted hydroxy-1,3-propanedione, dioxane-water.

Introduction

Substituted hydroxy-1,3-propanediones (β-diketones) are important as potential antimicrobial¹, antiviral², anti-inflammatory, antibacterial agents³, diketones are found to possess biological activity. In addition to fungicidal activity, diketones specially chlorodiketones are found to possess antihelminthic activities⁴. It is reported that the substituted diketones which are different in nature act as insecticides, bactericides, pharmaceuticals and fungicidal.

The lanthanide compounds have remarkable importance in every day life^{5,6}. More explicitly in the previous decades their use in various organic technical processes led to a rapid growth especially in the field of complexes. In recent years the luminescence properties of rare earth metal complexes with different β-diketones have been widely studied due to their use in fabrication of polymer light emitting diodes to enable low cost, full colour, flat panel display. The effect of dielectric constants on pK and log K values is reported by many workers⁷⁻⁹.

The ionic strength is an electrical current produced by the ions of inert salt in solution which is one of the characteristics of liquid. The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants are strongly affected by ionic strength of the medium. Sawalakhe *et al.*¹⁰ have investigated the

stability constants of Cu^{II} complexes with some substituted diketones at various ionic strength. Thakur *et al.*¹¹ have investigated the stability constants of Cu^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes with some substituted propane-dione at 0.1 ionic strengths pH-metrically. Agrawal *et al.*¹² studied stability constants of Co^{II}, Sr^{II}, Pr^{II} complexes with substituted azoles at various ionic strength. The influence of ionic strengths on complex equilibria of substituted pyrazoles with Sm^{III} and Pr^{III} studied by Naik *et al.*¹³. The dissociation constants of L-2-amino-3-hydroxypropanoic acid¹⁴ have been determined at various ionic strengths. The stability constants of complexation of VO₂⁺ with glycine discussed the effect of ionic strengths on protonation and complexation¹⁵. The effect of ionic strength on N-(trihydroxymethyl)glycine (Tricine)¹⁶ with transition metal ion Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes have been studied.

In present work Cr^{III} and La^{III} metal ions complexes with HB2CP and HB4NP at various ionic strengths in 70% dioxane-water mixture medium have been investigated by Calvin-Bjerrum pH metric technique at (29 ± 0.1 °C). The system has been studied at 0.02, 0.04, 0.06, 0.08 and 0.10 mol dm⁻³ ionic strength by varying the concentrations of sodium perchlorate.

Materials and solutions :

The ligands [HB2CP] (L_1) and [HB4NP] (L_2) were synthesized in the laboratory by known literature method. The purity of these compounds exceeds 99.5% and structures were confirmed by NMR, IR and melting points. The stock solutions of the ligands were prepared by dissolving required amount of ligands in a minimum volume of dioxane subsequently diluted to final volume. Metal ions solutions were prepared by dissolving metal nitrate (Sigma-Aldrich) and standardised by EDTA titration method as discussed in literature¹⁷. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution was prepared by dissolving the AnalaR pellets in deionised water and solution was standardised¹⁸. The stock solution of perchloric acid was prepared and used after standardization¹⁹.

Measurements :

All measurements were carried out at $(29 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C})$. Systronic microprocessor based pH meter with magnetic stirrer used for pH measurements. The sensitivity of pH meter is 0.01 units. The instrument could read pH in the range 0.00 to 14.00 in the steps of 0.005. The pH meter was switched on half an hour before starting the titration for initial warm up of the instrument. It was calibrated before each titration with an aqueous standard buffer solution of pH 7.00 and 9.20 at $(29 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C})$ prepared from a 'Qualigens' buffer tablets. The hydrogen ion concentration was measured with combined glass electrode.

Procedure :

The experimental procedure involved the titrations of

(i) Free acid HClO_4 (0.01 mol dm^{-3})

(ii) Free acid HClO_4 (0.01 mol dm^{-3}) and ligand ($20 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$)

(iii) Free acid HClO_4 (0.01 mol dm^{-3}) and ligand ($20 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and metal ion ($4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide ($0.142 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) solution using Calvin-Bjerrum and Calvin-Wilson pH titration techniques. The ionic strength of all the solutions were maintained constant by adding appropriate amount of NaClO_4 solution. All titrations were carried out in 70% dioxane-water mixture and readings were recorded for each 0.1 ml addition. The curves of pH against volume of NaOH solution were plotted²⁰⁻²².

Results and discussion

The extent of deviation may be the dissociation of -OH group. Substituted hydroxy-1,3-propanedione may be considered as a monobasic acid having one replaceable H^+ ion from phenolic -OH group and can be represented as

The titration data were used to construct the curves [acid curve (A), acid + ligand curve (A + L) and acid + ligand + metal ion curve (A + L + M)] between volumes of NaOH against pH.

Table 1. Proton-ligand formation number (n_A) at $(29 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C})$ and at ionic strength $\mu = 0.008 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ in 70%, dioxane-water mixture

Ligand	pH	V_1	V_2	$(V_2 - V_1)$	n_A	
HB2CP (L_1)	5.50	3.1312	3.2500	0.1187	0.8302	
	5.75	3.1500	3.2625	0.1250	0.8213	
	6.00	3.1562	3.2750	0.1250	0.8213	
	6.25	3.1625	3.3000	0.1437	0.7945	
	6.50	3.1625	3.3125	0.1500	0.7856	
	6.75	3.1656	3.3375	0.1719	0.7546	
	7.00	3.1718	3.3500	0.1782	0.7461	
	7.25	3.1750	3.3750	0.2000	0.7142	
	7.50	3.1812	3.4062	0.2250	0.6785	
	7.75	3.1875	3.4500	0.2625	0.6230	
	8.00	3.1968	3.5062	0.3094	0.5582	
	8.25	3.2062	3.5500	0.3437	0.5089	
	8.50	3.2125	3.6000	0.3875	0.4466	
	HB4NP (L_2)	6.75	3.1625	3.4375	0.275	0.6069
		7.00	3.1687	3.4500	0.2812	0.5980
7.25		3.1750	3.4650	0.2937	0.5802	
7.50		3.1812	3.4812	0.3000	0.5712	
7.75		3.1875	3.5000	0.3125	0.5534	
8.00		3.2000	3.5125	0.3125	0.5535	
8.25		3.2125	3.5250	0.3125	0.5536	
8.50		3.2187	3.5375	0.3187	0.5449	
8.75		3.2312	3.5500	0.3188	0.5459	
9.00		3.2437	3.5680	0.3250	0.5361	
9.25		3.2562	3.5812	0.3250	0.5361	
9.50		3.2687	3.6000	0.3313	0.5278	
9.75		3.2750	3.6250	0.3500	0.5008	
10.00		3.2875	3.6437	0.3562	0.4920	
10.25		3.3000	3.6625	0.3625	0.4832	
10.50	3.3125	3.6750	0.3625	0.4832		

The proton-ligand formation number n_A were calculated by Irving and Rossotti expression (Table 1),

$$n_A = \gamma - \frac{(E_0 + N)(V_2 - V_1)}{(V_0 + V_1) T_L^0} \quad (1)$$

where γ denotes the number of dissociable protons, N is the concentration of sodium hydroxide ($0.142 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), $(V_2 - V_1)$ is the measure of displacement of the ligand curve relative to acid curve, where V_2 and V_1 are the volume of alkali added to reach the same pH reading to get accurate values of $(V_2 - V_1)$: the titration curves were drawn on an enlarged scale: E^0 and T_L^0 are the resultant concentration of perchloric acid and concentration of ligand, respectively. V_0 is the initial volume of reaction mixture (50 cm^3). Proton-ligand stability constant pK values of ligands were calculated by algebraic method point wise calculation and also, estimated from formation curves n_A vs pH (half integral method) by noting pH at which $n_A = 0.5$ (Bjerrum 1957).

Metal-ligand stability constants ($\log K$) were determined by the half integral method by plotting n vs pL . The experimental n values determined using expression,

$$n = \frac{(E_0 + N)(V_3 - V_2)}{m_2 (V_0 + V_2) T_m^0} \quad (2)$$

where N , E_0 , V_0 and V_2 have same significance as in eq. (1), V_3 is the volume of NaOH added in the metal ion titration to attain the given pH reading and T_m^0 ($4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) is the concentration of metal ion in reaction mixture.

The pK values of ligand and $\log K$ values of Cr^{III} and La^{III} metal ion complexes with [HB4CP] and [HB4AP] at various ionic strength were calculated by Irving and Rossotti's method are set out in Tables 2 and 3. It could

Table 2. Proton-ligand stability constant (pK) of ligands [L_1 and L_2] at various ionic strengths (μ) in 70% dioxane-water

Ligand	μ	$\sqrt{\mu}$	$\sqrt{\mu}$		pK
		$1 + \sqrt{\mu}$	$(1 + \sqrt{\mu}) - 0.3\sqrt{\mu}$		
HB2CP [L_1]	0.10	0.3162	0.2402	0.1453	7.9300
	0.08	0.2828	0.2204	0.1355	8.3054
	0.06	0.2449	0.1967	0.1232	8.4300
	0.04	0.2000	0.1666	0.1066	9.3062
	0.02	0.1414	0.1239	0.8148	9.8600
HB4NP [L_2]	0.10	0.3162	0.2402	0.1453	9.0005
	0.08	0.2828	0.2204	0.1355	9.5708
	0.06	0.2449	0.1967	0.1232	9.6250
	0.04	0.2000	0.1666	0.1066	10.4500
	0.02	0.1414	0.1239	0.8148	11.1250

be observed that pK and $\log K$ values are found to decrease with increasing ionic strength that in accordance with Debye-Huckel theory. The $pK/\log K$ values were employed to calculate the thermodynamic constants with the help of Bronsted equation²³.

$$\log K = \log K^0 + A \cdot \Delta z^2 \cdot \sqrt{\mu} \quad (3)$$

and

$$pK = pK^0 - A \cdot \Delta z^2 \cdot \sqrt{\mu} \quad (4)$$

where A is the Debye-Huckel constant, Δz^2 is difference in the square of the charges of product and reactant ions and K^0 formation constant at zero ionic strength.

The system has been studied at 0.02, 0.04, 0.06, 0.08 and 0.10 mol dm^{-3} ionic strengths by varying the concentration of sodium perchlorate. In addition to sodium perchlorate, the titrating system contained ions from perchloric acid, metal nitrate and sodium hydroxide. The total ionic strength (μ) of the medium is calculated by following expression.

$$\mu = 1/2 \sum C_i Z_i^2 \quad (5)$$

where C_i and Z_i are the concentration and valency of metal ions respectively.

The values of pK , $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were plotted against $\sqrt{\mu}$, which gave straight lines. The magnitude of Δz^2 and slopes were calculated from graphs (Tables 3 and 4) The data obtained of pK and $\log K$ could be used to know the mechanism of complexation equilibria. The expected and observed values for Δz^2 for the corresponding dissociation and association reaction equilibria are given (Tables 4 and 5). It is observed that slope values (observed) of pK and $\log K$ are less than the expected values. Those values do not give conclusive evidence regarding the magnitude of charge of reacting species except the information that these are oppositely charged. The discrepancy may be due to the limited applicability of Bronsted equation.

The plots of $pK/\log K$ vs $[\sqrt{\mu}/(1 + \sqrt{\mu})]$ and $[\sqrt{\mu}/(1 + \sqrt{\mu}) - 0.3\sqrt{\mu}]$ are also plotted and are straight line and slope values were determined. It showed that modified Debye-Huckel equation also did not show much improvement in the slope values. This may be due to the fact that value for closest distance approach 'a' is fixed (3.33 \AA). The discrepancy between observed and expected slope values was thought of to be due to the concentration and not activity terms used in the equation of stability constants.

Table 3. Metal-ligand stability constant (log K) of various system at various ionic strengths (μ) in 70% dioxane-water

μ	$\sqrt{\mu}$	$\sqrt{\mu}$		log K_1	log K_2	log $K_1 - \log K_2$
		$1 + \sqrt{\mu}$	$(1 + \sqrt{\mu}) - 0.3\sqrt{\mu}$			
System : Cr ^{III} -HB2CP [L ₁]						
0.10	0.3162	0.2402	0.1453	6.0750	4.8250	1.2500
0.08	0.2828	0.2204	0.1355	7.3125	5.7500	1.5625
0.06	0.2449	0.1967	0.1232	7.7665	6.0750	1.6915
0.04	0.2000	0.166	0.1066	8.7234	6.1729	2.5505
0.02	0.1414	0.1239	0.8148	9.6428	6.8012	2.8416
System : La ^{III} -HB2CP [L ₁]						
0.10	0.3162	0.2402	0.1453	6.4877	5.9077	0.5800
0.08	0.2828	0.2204	0.1355	7.3000	7.0400	0.2600
0.06	0.2449	0.1967	0.1232	7.7300	7.1500	0.5800
0.04	0.2000	0.166	0.1066	7.9620	7.6000	0.3620
0.02	0.1414	0.1239	0.8148	8.8100	8.3200	0.4900
System : Cr ^{III} -HB4NP [L ₂]						
0.10	0.3162	0.2402	0.1453	7.1000	5.3375	1.7625
0.08	0.2828	0.2204	0.1355	8.4750	7.3750	1.1000
0.06	0.2449	0.1967	0.1232	8.6750	7.9250	0.7500
0.04	0.2000	0.166	0.1066	10.3502	8.6173	1.7329
0.02	0.1414	0.1239	0.8148	11.1100	9.4120	1.6980
System : La ^{III} -HB4NP [L ₂]						
0.10	0.3162	0.2402	0.1453	8.3875	7.1250	1.2625
0.08	0.2828	0.2204	0.1355	8.7925	7.3500	1.4425
0.06	0.2449	0.1967	0.1232	9.0123	7.8545	1.1578
0.04	0.2000	0.166	0.1066	10.0732	8.0681	2.0051
0.02	0.1414	0.1239	0.8148	10.8500	8.4750	2.3750

Table 4. Slopes and Δz^2 values from the plots of pK/log K vs $\sqrt{\mu}$

System	pK vs $\sqrt{\mu}$		log K_1 vs $\sqrt{\mu}$		log K_2 vs $\sqrt{\mu}$	
	-Slope	Δz^2	-Slope	Δz^2	-Slope	Δz^2
HB2CP [L ₁]	11.428	22.1274	-	-	-	-
HB4NP [L ₂]	19.807	37.0610	-	-	-	-
Cr ^{III} -HB2CP [L ₁]	-	-	16.5957	-32.1559	7.6190	-14.7626
La ^{III} -HB2CP [L ₁]	-	-	12.6415	-24.44342	12.6315	-24.4749
Cr ^{III} -HB4NP [L ₂]	-	-	23.3333	-45.2108	15.7142	-30.4479
La ^{III} -HB4NP [L ₂]	-	-	14.5833	-28.2567	8.1250	-15.7430

Table 5. The different possible reactions and observed and expected values of Δz^2 for corresponding dissociation or association equilibria of various systems

System	Constant	Reaction equilibria	Δz^2	
			Expected	Observed
HB2CP [L ₁]	pK	HL \rightleftharpoons H ⁺ + L ⁻	2.0	22.1274
HB4NP [L ₂]	pK	HL \rightleftharpoons H ⁺ + L ⁻	2.0	37.0610
Cr ^{III} -HB2CP [L ₁]	log K_1	L ⁻ + Cr ³⁺ \rightleftharpoons (CrL) ²⁺	-6.0	-32.1559
	log K_2	(CrL) ²⁺ + L ⁻ \rightleftharpoons (CrL ₂) ⁺	-4.0	-14.7626

La ^{III} -HB2CP [L ₁]	log K ₁	L ⁻ + La ³⁺ ⇌ (LaL) ²⁺	-6.0	-24.4342
	log K ₂	(LaL) ²⁺ + L ⁻ ⇌ (LaL ₂) ⁺	-4.0	-24.4749
Cr ^{III} -HB4NP [L ₂]	log K ₁	L ⁻ + Cr ³⁺ ⇌ (CrL) ²⁺	-6.0	-45.2108
	log K ₂	(CrL) ²⁺ + L ⁻ ⇌ (CrL ₂) ⁺	-4.0	-30.4479
La ^{III} -HB4NP [L ₂]	log K ₁	L ⁻ + La ³⁺ ⇌ (LaL) ²⁺	-6.0	-28.2567
	log K ₂	(LaL) ³⁺ + L ⁻ ⇌ (LaL ₂) ⁺	-4.0	-15.7430

Thermodynamics stability constants (pK⁰/log K⁰) :

The thermodynamic stability constants (pK⁰ and log K⁰) are calculated at zero ionic strength from various plots (Table 6).

Table 6. Thermodynamic dissociation constants at zero ionic strength (pK⁰ and log K⁰)

System	Plot	(pK ⁰ and log K ⁰)
HB2CP [L ₁]	pK vs √μ	11.15
	pK vs [√μ/(1 + √μ)]	11.60
	pK vs [√μ/(1 + √μ)] - 0.3√μ	11.10
HB4NP [L ₂]	pK vs √μ	12.90
	pK vs [√μ/(1 + √μ)]	13.10
	pK vs [√μ/(1 + √μ)] - 0.3√μ	12.50
Cr ^{III} -HB2CP [L ₁]	log K ₁ vs √μ	11.95
	log K ₁ vs [√μ/(1 + √μ)]	12.40
	log K ₁ vs [√μ/(1 + √μ)] - 0.3√μ	12.00
	log K ₂ vs √μ	7.85
	log K ₂ vs [√μ/(1 + √μ)]	8.20
La ^{III} -HB2CP [L ₁]	log K ₁ vs √μ	10.60
	log K ₁ vs [√μ/(1 + √μ)]	10.95
	log K ₁ vs [√μ/(1 + √μ)] - 0.3√μ	10.75
	log K ₂ vs √μ	10.10
	log K ₂ vs [√μ/(1 + √μ)]	10.20
Cr ^{III} -HB4NP [L ₂]	log K ₁ vs √μ	14.15
	log K ₁ vs [√μ/(1 + √μ)]	14.50
	log K ₁ vs [√μ/(1 + √μ)] - 0.3√μ	14.20
	log K ₂ vs √μ	11.60
	log K ₂ vs [√μ/(1 + √μ)]	11.90
La ^{III} -HB4NP [L ₂]	log K ₁ vs √μ	12.40
	log K ₁ vs [√μ/(1 + √μ)]	12.90
	log K ₁ vs [√μ/(1 + √μ)] - 0.3√μ	12.30
	log K ₂ vs √μ	9.62
	log K ₂ vs [√μ/(1 + √μ)]	10.00
	log K ₂ vs [√μ/(1 + √μ)] - 0.3√μ	9.70

It can be seen from Table 5 that the agreement of the thermodynamic constants (pK⁰ and log K⁰) obtained from various plots for a particular system are approximately same.

Conclusion :

At (29 ± 0.1 °C), Calvin-Bjerrum pH metric technique used to investigate the complex formation between Cr^{III} and La^{III} metal ions with HB2CP and HB4NP at various ionic strength in 70% dioxane-water mixture medium and studies the influence of various ionic strength of medium on complex equilibria from observation, it is concluded that as ionic strength of medium increases (0.02 to 0.1 mol dm⁻³), stability constants (log K₁ and log K₂) decreases i.e. complex formation stability decreases.

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